

A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY ON THE STRAIN RATE DEPENDENCE FOR ELASTO-PLASTIC RESPONSE OF CROSSLINKED EPOXY

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Keywords: Epoxy polymer, Strain rate, Elasto-plastic, Deformation mechanism,
Molecular dynamics simulations

ABSTRACT

In this study, elasto-plastic deformation mechanism on epoxy polymer was investigated considering effect of crosslink density with the aid of molecular dynamics simulations. From the equilibrated unit cells, uniaxial loading-unloading simulations were conducted to understand the origin of the plastic deformation. The vdW and dihedral angle energy are of the prime potential energy components inducing permanent deformations. To observe the microscopic structure of the unit cells, the change of the free volume and dihedral angles during the loading-unloading simulations were monitored rigorously. Consequently, the fundamental mechanism behind plastic deformations of epoxy systems are attributed to the permanent variations of free volume and dihedral angle after unloading. The benzene ring-related torsional types are of primary factors generating a permanent plastic deformation due to the inherent rigidity of benzene ring structure. The effect of crosslink density on the plastic deformation was further examined considering the strain rate dependency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy polymers has been widely used in polymer science and related industry because of their high mechanical strength, thermal stability, high water resistance and long working time attributed to crosslinked molecular network structure. Depending on the chemical composition, curing agent and molecular weight, it is possible to obtain broad range of thermo-mechanical properties. Therefore, it can be used in many applications such as a resin of nanocomposites, electronic packing system, adhesives and aircraft fuselage. There are many applications using this multifunctional material. For example, epoxy polymers are good insulator in electrical system and can protect the electrical components from short circuiting, dust and moisture. When the nano-sized particle is embedded into the epoxy polymer, the thermomechanical response of the resin can be significantly enhanced and adjustable its property according to the various particle size and loading conditions [1-3]. Rubber-like particles and/or thermoplastic polymer can also be inserted in the epoxy network to overcome the brittleness of epoxy polymer.

As far as the durability of epoxy material was concerned for a mechanical purpose, it is relatively easy to be exposed in severe thermo-mechanical loading and physical aging environment, resulting in large deformations on the material. Thus, the understanding of plastic deformation behaviour of epoxy systems is of primary interest. In terms of microscopic point of view, however, an atomistic

interpretation for the elasto-plastic deformation mechanism of epoxy polymers is limited as of yet.

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are one of promising ways to understand the microscopic characteristics of polymer material, providing a physical insight in terms of atomistic nature. Some molecular dynamics simulation researches related to polymer physics were reported. It was reported by D. Hossain et al. that the deformation mechanism of thermoplastic polymer, polyethylene, was attributed to the non-bond interactions and the trans-gauche phase transformations of torsional angle distribution [4]. Sundararaghavan et al. confirmed the importance of kinking process on the compression behaviour of epoxy using MD simulations [5]. Jatin et al. showed that the typical strain softening is directly related with the burst of free volume and strain hardening is governed by non-bond part interaction. They also observed that the irreversible dihedral angle change after unloading [6].

When it comes to dealing with the deformation characteristics of polymer materials, another important aspect is strain rate dependency due to the viscoelastic nature of polymers. Generally, with the high strain rates, high yield point was observed as a result of relatively limited relaxation time in both experiments and simulations. Thus, the rate-dependency on deformation behaviour of epoxy polymer needs to be considered.

The objective of this study is to characterize the plastic deformation behavior of crosslinked epoxy polymers using full-atomic MD simulations. Considering various crosslinking density as well as strain rate conditions, the intrinsic physics of elasto-plastic deformation mechanism of epoxy polymer are discussed herein,

2 MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION METHOD

2.1 CLOSE CONTACT METHOD

Unlike with the previous research about MD simulations of thermoset epoxy using the representative molecule method, the study employs the close contact method to mimic the realistic crosslinking procedure. This method defines the cutoff distance between reactive atoms of curing agent and epoxy chain, and then make covalent bonds between reactive atoms within the predefined cutoff distance. To reach the desired crosslinking density, the cutoff distance was increased and this process was repeated iteratively. In every crosslinking procedure, NVT ensemble was performed to relax residual stress among epoxy system after the formation of new crosslinks. Crosslinked epoxy polymers with different degree of crosslink ratio were constructed using triglycidyl-amino-phenol (TGAP) as an epoxy resin and diamino-diphenylsulfone (DDS) as a curing agent.

2.2 UNIT CELL CONSTRUCTION

By different crosslink ratio as mentioned previous section 2.1, 34%, 50%, and 70% of epoxy models are constructed. Each cell has a shape of a cube and length of unit cell is 34 Å. Total number of unit cell is 4702. Each cell was minimized using the conjugate gradient method. Then unit cells are equilibrated NVT dynamics at 300K for 600ps followed by NPT dynamics at 300K and 1atm for 1200ps using Material Studio® 5.5, a commercial software package. Then equilibrated cells are relaxed one more time for 2ns NVT, NPT ensemble at the same condition of previous ensemble using a parallel molecular dynamics code, LAMMPS. The relaxed crosslinked cells have a good agreement with experimental epoxy density. All the procedure is performed through polymer consistent force field (PCFF). The resultant epoxy unit cell is represented in Fig.1

2.3 UNIAXIAL TENSILE SIMULATION

Uniaxial tensile simulations are performed with the aid of LAMMPS. Strain was defined gradually and NPT ensemble was performed at every strain increment to ensure the relaxation of unit cells. Strain was increased up to 0.4. Both loading and unloading simulations was performed on the same thermomechanical conditions at 1atm and room temperature (300K). The unloading was performed until the unit cells have no stress value, stress-free point. Each considered crosslinked model are simulated three times along x, y, and z directions to reduce the effect of uncertainty caused by the high number of possible chain conformations. All the simulations considered Poisson's ratio by giving

atmosphere condition. Furthermore, to observe the strain rate dependency, several kinds of strain rate ($10^{10}/\text{sec}$, $10^{9.5}/\text{sec}$, $10^9/\text{sec}$, $10^{8.5}/\text{sec}$, $10^8/\text{sec}$ and $10^7/\text{sec}$) are considered.

Figure 1: Constructed epoxy unit cell and monomers.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 INTERNAL ENERGY DISTRIBUTION DURING LOADING-UNLOADING

Through uniaxial loading-unloading simulations, we can plot the internal energy profiles as shown in Fig.2. All the profiles are averaged 9 times assuming isotropic condition. In the simulations, we derived all the energy profiles such as bond, angle, torsion, and non-bond interaction during the deformations. From the extent of accommodation of deformation energy among the internal energy profiles, we concluded that vdW and dihedral angle related molecular movements are chosen as the most important molecular behavior affecting the plastic deformation of epoxy. The purple ascendant curve shows loading curve and blue is unloading. Unloading simulation was carried out to the stress free point where unit cells have zero stress. In all the profiles, there exists irreversible energy gap between initial point and stress free point. It means that not all increased internal energy during the deformation dissipated, when unloading is over. It can be thought that the residual energy corresponding to the irreversible energy gap shown in the Fig.2 was relaxed through inter-, intra-molecular movements. That is, plastic molecular behavior has progressed. Therefore, we can employ the irreversible energy gap as a criterion of plastic deformation. To be more specific, slope of the vdW energy curve is steep in the low strain range and become gentle at the high strain range, which corresponds to the high slope of potential energy at the elastic range. It is equivalent to the shape of L-J potential profiles describing the non-bond interaction energy. The shape of vdW energy profile shows small increasing as the distance between two atoms become large. On the contrary, dihedral angle energy shows no meaningful change at the low strain and make a value gradually at high strain range. This results suggests that dihedral angle energy is closely related with plastic behavior of epoxy polymer.

3.2 FREE VOLUME ANALYSIS

The vdW energy was affected greatly by intra-molecular relative atomic position. To effectively figure out the molecular movement, we can observe the free volume evolution along the strain. Amorphous polymer is composed of part of chains and void which corresponds to the free volume determined by van der Waals surface of the molecules. This part is free for redistribution in glassy polymer [7]. Thus the change of free volume evolution can indicates the degree of chain relaxation during the deformation. Fig.3 represents the free volume versus strain profile. Like the potential energy graph in Fig.2, the free volume profile is also composed of loading and unloading part. This figure is very similar with the vdW energy profile. As you can see in the Fig.3, free volume is increased more rapidly at the range of the low strain. This means all of increased volume caused by the

tensile strain is directly represented as a part of free volume. It is because that free volume is not sufficient for polymer chains to fill the increased free volume as a result of chain redistribution. As the strain increases, sufficient free volume makes it possible to redistribute the polymer chains during the deformation. This rapid relaxation in the high strain range results in plastic behavior of epoxy polymer. In the figure of the free volume, there exists irreversible free volume like as the energy profiles, when unloading is over. This is the powerful evidence of irreversible intra-molecular redistribution of chains.

Figure 2: Internal energy curve of loading and unloading simulation.

Figure 3: Free volume evolution of loading and unloading simulation.

3.3 DIHEDRAL ENERGY AND ANGLE ANALYSIS

As shown in Fig.2, dihedral angle energy is increased at the range of the high strain and has the irreversible energy gap. It is concerned with the effect of dihedral angle change on the plastic deformation. In the previous research of thermoplastic polymer, it was pointed out that dihedral angle distribution was changed a lot when plastic deformation of polymer is initiated [1]. In the case of

thermoset polymer which is the target materials of this research, there is no visible change of total dihedral angle distribution compared with thermoplastic polymer. It is quite obvious, because thermoset polymer is highly crosslinked structure unlike just simple hydrocarbon, which hinders polymer chains from redistributing during the deformation. So, we can thought differently that there will be the particular types of dihedral angle which is concerned with irreversible molecular behavior. Using the below dihedral angle potential describing the dihedral angle energy of class II force field, the dihedral angle energy through different types of dihedral angle was calculated. The dihedral angle energy is composed of dihedral term E_d and other cross terms to describe the coupled effect with other parameters like bond and angle.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E &= E_d + E_{mbt} + E_{at} + E_{aat} + E_{bb13} \\
 E_d &= \sum_{n=1}^3 K_n [1 - \cos(n\phi - \phi_n)] \\
 E_{mbt} &= (r_{jk} - r_2)[A_1 \cos(\phi) + A_2 \cos(2\phi) + A_3 \cos(3\phi)] \\
 E_{mbt} &= (r_{ij} - r_1)[B_1 \cos(\phi) + B_2 \cos(2\phi) + B_3 \cos(3\phi)] + \\
 &\quad (r_{kl} - r_3)[C_1 \cos(\phi) + C_2 \cos(2\phi) + C_3 \cos(3\phi)] \\
 E_{at} &= (\theta_{ijk} - \theta_1)[D_1 \cos(\phi) + D_2 \cos(2\phi) + D_3 \cos(3\phi)] + \\
 &\quad (\theta_{jkl} - \theta_3)[E_1 \cos(\phi) + E_2 \cos(2\phi) + E_3 \cos(3\phi)] \\
 E_{aat} &= M(\theta_{ijk} - \theta_1)(\theta_{jkl} - \theta_2) \cos(\phi) \\
 E_{bb13} &= N(r_{ij} - r_1)(r_{jk} - r_3)
 \end{aligned}$$

E represents the total dihedral angle energy shown in Fig.2. All the coefficient is determined by torsional types in the class II force field, while variables of dihedral angle ϕ , bond length r , and angle θ with subscript i, j, k and l are exported from the atomic position of unit cell. The subscripts i, j, k and l denote the four atoms consisting of dihedral angle. Almost all terms is made up of trigonometric function.

We divided the dihedral energy of Fig.2 by the different torsional types which is determined by kind of atoms. Total 53 kind of dihedral types was calculated, and the four major dihedral types related with the plastic behavior were selected as you can see in Fig.4. The brown color is type 1 consisting of four carbon in the benzene ring. The orange color is type 5 consisting of two carbon of benzene ring, linked oxygen and carbon. The yellow-green color, type 9 is made up of two carbon of benzene ring, linked nitrogen and carbon. The green color, type 46 is composed of two carbon of benzene ring, sulfur and another carbon of linked benzene ring. These torsional types is shown in the Fig.5.

In Fig.4, we also depicted the change of dihedral potential energy for each considered type. Simulation time from zero to 400 picoseconds corresponds to the loading, and the remaining part presents unloading. Through the dihedral energy profile, we can observe which torsional type stores the deformation energy after unloading process is over and reach to stress-free point. During the elastic deformation (<10ps), torsional energy of type 1 shows substantial increase, which occupies almost all of the increase in the dihedral energy shown in Fig.2. However, the energy of type 1 is sustained during the plastic deformation and recovered to the initial point after unloading simulation has performed (400~500ps). Thus, we can conclude that type 1 does not induce plastic deformation in the epoxy polymer. Type 46 also shows similar behavior with type 1. The increase of dihedral energy during loading simulation is completely recovered after unloading process is over and reach stress-free point. In other words, the type 1 and type 46 are not involved with the plastic molecular behavior. In case of type 5, it has decreasing section at 0~100ps like the type 46. The different thing is that it still maintain the value of energy though unloading is finished. Type 9 shows an ideal plastic behavior, the dihedral energy of type 9 representing the gradual increase which is similar with the increase of total dihedral angle energy of Fig.2. When unloading is over, it still retain the energy of $20kcal/mol$.

Now we have known the major dihedral types of deformation and their energy profile tendency. To understand the dihedral angle behavior related with the energy profile, we drew the representative dihedral angle change of four major dihedral types in Fig.5. Though it is just one case among the many dihedral angles of certain type, overall angle change has the similar tendency. As shown in Fig.4, angle change is composed of loading and unloading parts. In the case of type 1, there is no change in angle with the simulation time. It is result of the benzene ring sticking to be in the same plane. Thus the dihedral angle vibrated around the zero. Actually, rather than the effect of dihedral angle, the increase of dihedral energy of type 1 has a lot to do with coupled terms for bond length. Type 46 shows reversible tendency in dihedral angle behavior. Angle change in the loading range go back to its initial state. But the type 5 and type 9 shows abrupt or gradual change of angle and cannot go to initial angle state. While the atoms of benzene ring stick to be in the same plane during the deformation, the atoms connected with benzene ring have the relatively large movement resulting in irreversible dihedral angle change. That is, it is mixed effect between position-unchangeable property of carbons in benzene ring and position-changeable property of connected atoms. Consequently, torsional type structure like type 5 and type 9 shows plastic deformation. Type 46 is more constrained by the two benzene ring compared with type 5 and type 9. That benzene-constrained effect blocks the meaningful angle change.

Figure 4: The dihedral energy change of major dihedral types with the simulation time increment.

Figure 5: The dihedral angle change of major dihedral types with the simulation time increment.

3.4 EFFECT OF CROSSLINK DENSITY ON THE DEFORMATION MECHANISM

From now on, we have investigated the deformation mechanisms of epoxy polymer. Non-bond interaction and dihedral angle change of certain types works as an important cause. It is important to note that this two internal energies are affected by crosslink density. It was thought that the degree of constrained molecular movement by crosslink density would have an effect on the vdW interaction. In regard of dihedral angle energy, the number of torsional type 9 is increased with the increment of crosslink density. Fig.6 represents the free volume profile and dihedral angle energy profile of different two crosslink density.

The low crosslink density shows dramatic decrease of slope and has a constant slope after the strain reached about 0.1. But at the high crosslink density, it shows consistent increase of slope and has a high free volume percentage as compared with low crosslink density. It is due to the extent of constrain resulted from the crosslink density. At the low strain, as mentioned section 3.2, there are no sufficient free volume for chain relaxation. Thus this strain range shows no significant difference between two different crosslink densities. As free volume increases, less constrained epoxy chains of low crosslink density start to relax through free volume. But it is hard for constrained chains of high crosslink density to rapidly relax. That is, it is crosslink density that makes the difference in free volume change at plastic strain range resulted from chain redistribution. More redistribution of low crosslink density is favorable to the plastic deformation.

As for the effect on dihedral angle energy, crosslink procedure itself is to increase the number of dihedral angle type 9. As shown in Fig.4, dihedral type 9 increases the total dihedral energy as the strain increases. The simulation time of 200ps nearly corresponds to the value of strain 0.2 when total dihedral energy begins to increase. Therefore low crosslink density shows no gap of dihedral angle energy which is shown in high crosslink density. The effect of crosslink density on plastic deformation work reversely regarding these two aspects.

Figure 6: Free volume evolution and dihedral energy of different crosslink density, as the strain is increased up to 0.4.

4 STRAIN RATES DEPENDENCY

Fig.7 represent the internal energy profile as strain increases. Table 1 is the result of yield stress with the different strain rates. As shown in the table 1, overall tendency of yield stress is decreased with the decrement of strain rates in all of crosslink density. These tendency is previously identified in theoretical and experimental many researches. In the Fig.7, there exist gradual decrease of all the internal potentials. It is caused by the relaxation time through different strain rates. As the relaxation time increases, the amount of all the internal energy decreases. But the overall profile of energy accommodation is not changed. That means deformation mechanism does not changed and is valid for the low strain rate range.

Strain rate \ Crosslink ratio	Strain rate					
	1e10	1e9.5	1e9	1e8.5	1e8	1e7
x34	189.20	152.49	125.38	96.80	95.68	-
x50	231.45	184.15	147.90	118.95	114.12	-
x70	244.65	205.17	181.02	143.42	123.10	124.16

Table 1: The fitted yield stress for different strain rates of three kinds of crosslink density.

Figure 7: Internal energy evolution of 0.7 crosslinked epoxy for the different strain rates

5 CONCLUSIONS

The deformation mechanism of crosslinked epoxy polymer has been investigated through well-defined molecular dynamics simulations. It is verified that the changes of vdW and dihedral potential energy are a prime origin for the plastic deformations by calculating the non-bond interaction of intermolecular movement and torsional angle change during the simulations. Through the free volume analysis and dihedral angle change profile, the change of microscopic structure during the deformation also can be estimated quantitatively. These nano-structural behaviors show good agreement with the energetical results of the bulk polymer model. The important design variable, crosslink density has the significant effect on the deformation mechanism, especially for the mobility and free volume change of the epoxy system. In particular, we find out that crosslinking participants generate new torsional types closely related with plastic deformation. Regarding on the strain rate, the deformation mechanism and its intrinsic phenomena is not changed remarkably.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work supported by DAPA and ADD under the contract No. UE135112GD.

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